

CURING OF EPOXY RESINS: A NANOSCALE VIEW

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy is undoubtedly one of the most successful matrix in the field of polymer composites. It attracts a lot of attention from researchers and industrials with the common objective to formulate a stiff, strong, and tough resin. Such goal can only be reached if the fundamental mechanisms which control the final properties of the resin are well understood and controlled. The nanoscale simulations techniques nowadays become effective approaches to complement high-tech experiments and offer an alternative route to understand the properties of complex systems. Among the various techniques developed over the past half-century, molecular dynamics has gained popularity thanks to both its simple principle and its efficiency in tackling versatile problems. However the key parameter of the simulation, the force field which models the interactions between the atoms, is traditionally classified as non-reactive, i.e. it cannot model the formation and disappearance of covalent bonds between functional chemical moieties. Modelling the curing process of an epoxy system remains therefore highly challenging. To circumvent this issue, the ReaxFF reactive force field is used for the first time to predict the reactivity of epoxy precursor and hardener molecules. It is capable of modelling non catalytic reactions between epoxide and amine groups as well as autocatalytic reactions between hydroxyl and amine groups. The formation of the 3D network is monitored by following either the number and mass of molecules or the number of reactive groups in the system. This original modelling work does not only mimic real systems but also gives a molecular view of the mechanisms which drive the curing process. This study is a first step toward the development of a multi-scale modelling framework aiming at giving a comprehensive view of the physical chemistry of nano engineered fiber reinforced composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The usage of epoxy is widespread and versatile with daily life (glue) as well as high technology applications (aerospace) especially in the field of polymer composites. This class of thermosets is often used in combination with synthetic (carbon, glass) or natural (flax, hemp) fibers to design composites with excellent mechanical properties. They are inherited from both the relatively high strength and stiffness of the matrix (compared to other polymer matrices) and its strong adhesion to fibers. Typically, epoxy resin are found in the form of a liquid mixture composed of epoxy precursors and curing agents (hardener) which present functional chemical moieties forming covalent bonds, i.e. a curing process is initiated. During processing, epoxy therefore undergoes a change of state: first liquid (uncured), epoxy progressively turns into a gel and finally into a solid as the curing process takes place. The final molecular structure is composed of a gigantic 3D network resulting from the complex chemical reactions occurring between the multi-functional molecules. Modifying the chemistry of the epoxy precursors and curing agents permits to fine tune the final mechanical properties of the cured system even if a compromise must always be achieved between stiffness, strength, and toughness. If chemists [1] can describe the different chemical reactions governing the formation of a cured epoxy, the influence of the surface of fibers or the presence of nanoparticles like

carbon nanotubes or graphene sheet on the curing process is still largely unknown. Experimental techniques like transmission electron microscopy or infra-red spectroscopy partially shed light on the physico-chemical processes occurring at these interfaces but such works remain very challenging. Fortunately, the simulation techniques nowadays become effective approaches to investigate such problems. Molecular dynamics (MD) [2], [3] is one of the most popular techniques thanks to its simplicity and free access. The key feature of these simulations is the choice of the forces which model the way atoms interact with one another. The availability of many force fields (DREIDING, COMPASS, OPLS, etc.) and open-source software (LAMMPS, TINKER, NAMD, etc.) is appealing and favors the spreading of such technique. However, most of the force fields are classified as non-reactive, i.e. they cannot model the formation or breakage of covalent bonds, a prerequisite to simulate the curing of epoxy resins. Previous studies either focused on uncured systems [4] or used a user-dependent distance criteria to trigger the formation of covalent bonds [5]–[9]. Odegard et al [10] recently proposed to predict the breakage of covalent bonds of an epoxy system with a reactive force field based on the ReaxFF [11], [12] formalism. Indeed, as the modelling of the curing of epoxy resins must cope with two apparent conflicting requirements, a large scale system to observe the network architecture (atomistic scale) and accurate description of bonds breaking and formation (electronic scale) [13], only specific force fields like ReaxFF can reliably model at the same time the physical and chemical interactions between epoxy precursors.

This work describes the methodology implemented to model the reactivity of the epoxy and hardener precursors using the ReaxFF formalism and how it was applied to monitor the curing of a nanoscale volume of RTM6 resin.

2 MATERIALS

Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-methylenedianiline (TGMDA) tetrafunctional epoxide and an aromatic diamine (hardener), 4,4'-methylenebis(2-isopropyl-6-methylaniline) (M-MIPA) (Figure 1) were selected as these monomers are some precursors of the HexFlow® RTM6 resin (Hexcel) developed to fulfil the requirements of the aerospace industries in Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). Also, with 4 reactive moieties (epoxy rings), TGMDA is a highly reactive monomer which makes it suitable to be tested in reactive nanoscale simulations.

Figure 1: Chemical formulae of the epoxy (left side) and hardener precursors (right side)

3 SIMULATION MODEL

3.1 Molecular Dynamics

The method consists of generating successive configurations of a molecular system by applying Newton's second law of motion to each atom. The force derives here from the ReaxFF (see next section) force field. The velocities and positions of the atoms were calculated from successive integrations via a velocity Verlet algorithm. The time step for the integration was 0.25 fs. The Nose-Hoover thermostat was used to control the temperature. The successive positions of the atoms were generated by the LAMMPS code [14].

To start the dynamics, initial positions of the atoms had to be prescribed. The atoms were randomly put in a three-dimensional box with periodic boundary conditions in the three directions to avoid side artefacts. This was followed by a short period of relaxation of the structure to relieve constraints involved in the construction step and to find an equilibrium initial configuration. A stoichiometric system composed of 10 TGMDA and 10 M-MIPA molecules was constructed following this procedure.

3.2 Force field

The development, from quantum chemical calculations (Density Functional Theory), of an appropriate force field to model the key reactions occurring during the curing process, is the prerequisite to any atomistic simulations. Such development is not straightforward as it requires not only to identify these reactions and their associated reaction paths but also to assess the values of the parameters required to model the bonds (stretching potential), angles (bending potential) and dihedral angles (torsion potential) as well as Van der Waals (Lennard-Jones potential) and electrostatic (Coulombic potential) interactions. The generated dataset is then used to train the ReaxFF force field. The number of free parameters required to parameterize the force field is however large so that the fitting procedure is somehow difficult to carry without a deep understanding of both the ReaxFF paradigm and the physico-chemistry of the modelled molecules. Fortunately, for epoxy, a force field has already been, to some extent, parameterized. Its main purpose is to model interactions between proteins and a graphene sheet [15] and is therefore adapted to predict epoxide reactions between epoxy rings and amine groups, the key reactions of the epoxy system. This property is actually a side effect of the protein force field parameterization but is highly beneficial to model epoxy system.

3.2 Validation

The reliability of the force field is first tested against a simple reaction between the NH_3 and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$ moieties. The accepted reaction path consisted in a two-step reaction for which the epoxy ring first opens, one proton is then transferred from the nitrogen to the oxygen atom. Such reaction is indeed accurately described by the force field (Figure 2), i.e. a $\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH}$ group is obtained. However, the energy barrier to be overcome by the reactants is high (Figure 3). In other words, the reaction cannot occur spontaneously within the timescale of a classical molecular dynamics simulation. The reaction must be driven by restraining the distances between the carbon and oxygen and the nitrogen and hydrogen of the respectively epoxy and amine groups. Alternative restraints like high temperature and high density systems were simulated but they did not permit to model the reaction. Thus, hereafter, the restraints on the distances will always be considered in the simulations. To relieve such restraints, the force field should be retrained against epoxy only and not protein data anymore. This work goes beyond the scope of this current work.

Figure 2: $\text{NH}_3\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$ reaction. Reactants (left side) and product (right side)

Figure 3: Energy barrier associated to the $\text{NH}_3\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}$ reaction

3.3 Chemical reactions

At least 2 reactions must be implemented to model the curing of epoxy and hardener precursors. A primary amine reacts with an epoxy ring to produce a secondary amine and an hydroxyl -OH group. The secondary amine can further react with a second epoxy ring to produce a tertiary amine. A third reaction can also be considered between a newly produced hydroxyl group and an epoxy ring. It yields an ether group (Figure 4). Again, thanks to the restraints on the distances, these reactions are properly depicted by the reactive force field.

Figure 4: Reactions between a primary amine, a secondary amine, and an hydroxyl group with epoxy rings, respectively at the top left, top right, and middle bottom

The standalone ReaxFF program can be used to run the molecular dynamics simulations but the open source LAMMPS program is preferably used in this study. It means that the restraints formulated in the standalone program had to be translated (from Morse to harmonic potentials) into the form of “fix restraints” specific to LAMMPS. The restraints must be strong enough to drive the reaction and thus guarantee the formation of a new molecule but also smooth enough to avoid the fragmentation of the reactants. Such trade-off was obtained using an additional harmonic potential with a spring coefficient increasing linearly from 10 to 1000 kcal/mol/Å over a period of 10.000 time steps.

This preliminary study focusing on the reactive groups permitted to assess the relevancy of the protein force field to model epoxy systems. To trigger the reactions, restraints must be added to the overall ReaxFF potentials to overcome the energy barrier which would prevent any reaction from occurring. However, the two-step reaction is well predicted.

3.4 Simulation methodology

TCL scripts were used to monitor the LAMMPS simulations. Their role is to create input files for LAMMPS and to check if the targeted reaction was completed or not. The procedure is the following: a first TCL script reads the connectivity table (provided when running LAMMPS and ReaxFF), identifies the atoms belonging to the reactive groups and assigns them a specific atom type in addition to the classical atom type definitions (from 1 to 4 for respectively classical carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen atom types and from 5 to 8 for carbon alpha, carbon beta, hydrogen amine, and nitrogen amine) (Figure 5). An input data file containing the initial positions of the atoms as well as their types properly defined is then created.

Figure 5: Atom type definition of the reactive atoms

A second script reads the data file, calculate the distances between all pairs of alpha carbon and nitrogen amine atoms (Figure 6). For every pair of atoms, i.e. every distance, a probability of reaction, p , is calculated following a simple linear rule (Figure 7). A random number is then generated (ζ) and compared to p : if $p > \zeta$, the reaction is accepted and a LAMMPS input file generated to model this reaction. If not, the next alpha carbon/nitrogen amine pair is tested. The input file is automatically written so that the energy barriers between the reactive groups and molecules are written to disk. When the simulation is over, the completion of the reaction is checked. In case of incomplete reaction (because of a too high energy barrier for example), the same simulation is run over a longer period (+ 5000 timesteps) with the objective to drive the reaction in a smoother way with greater chances of success. When the reaction is finally completed, the number of primary, secondary, and tertiary amines is updated and end criteria checked. They are of two types: the reaction fails a maximum number of time (partially cured system) or the number of primary and secondary amines is zero (fully cured system). Input and output files are stored in folders for every completed reaction. It facilitates a restart procedure and enables the addition of new components during the dynamics. The ideas described above and the way they are implemented are rather simple but it includes all the basic principles which should lead to a better understanding of the curing dynamics.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the script driven the LAMMPS simulation

Figure 7: Probability rule as a function of the distance between the alpha Carbon and Nitrogen amine

5 RESULTS

Figure 8 shows the initial and final molecular structures for a simulation run at 400K. It is visually impossible to assess the level of curing.

Figure 8: Left side, initial configuration, uncured system. Right side: final configuration, cured system.

However, the TCL scripts enable to monitor:

- the total energy of the system (Figure 9). It permits to check if the products of the reaction are more stable than the reactants (decrease of the total energy) and if an equilibrium configuration is reached.
- the number of failure per reaction (Figure 10). While the system cures, the rigidity of the 3D network increases and make it more difficult for molecules to react. It should be highlighted by an increasing number of failure versus curing.

Figure 9: Total energy versus time

Figure 10: Number of failure per reaction

- the evolution of the nitrogen amine type (Figure 11 and Figure 12). This output gives a detailed view of the curing process. Primary amines are first converted into secondary ones which are themselves converted into tertiary ones, i.e. the number of secondary amines reaches a maximum during curing when the autocatalytic reaction is not modelled. If this one is considered the picture becomes more complicated as secondary amines and hydroxyl oxygen (both created when a primary amine reacts with an epoxy ring) can both react with an epoxy ring. A fully cured system is characterized by a conversion of all the primary amine into tertiary amine.
- the number of molecules (Figure 11 and Figure 12). Theoretically the simulation should generate a single giant molecule but the reactive feature of the force field as well as the difficulty in completing a reaction can lead respectively to side products and partial curing. For example, without the auto-catalytic reaction, the simulation ends with 4 molecules, an unreacted hardener monomer, a water molecule, a propanone, and the 3D network.
- trajectory files of the reactive groups and molecules. These files help to visualize (via the VMD software) the displacements of the reactive groups and molecules.

Figure 11: Curing dynamics (Without autocatalytic reaction). Left side, evolution of the amine type during the curing process. Right side, number of molecules versus the curing process

Figure 12: Curing dynamics (With autocatalytic reaction). Left side, evolution of the amine type during the curing process. Right side, number of molecules versus the curing process

6 CONCLUSIONS

The ReaxFF force field was used to model the curing process of an epoxy model with success. If chemical reactions have to be driven via the addition of restraints, the basic physico-chemistry principles are respected. A simple algorithm is proposed to predict the curing process. It is implemented via TCL scripts monitoring the molecular dynamics simulations executed via the LAMMPS software. The analysis reveals the molecular mechanisms which drive the dynamics of the process, i.e. the high reactivity of the primary amines competes with the secondary amine and autocatalytic reactions. The next step is two-fold: first the validation of the proposed methodology will be performed via the graphitization of the cured system. The idea is to mimic a Differential Scanning Calorimetry experiment, a widespread and reliable technique to characterize thermosets. The cured system will be also mechanically loaded to explore the elastic and fracture properties of epoxy at the nanoscale with a specific interest given to the effects of surfaces (fibers and nano-inclusions).

Future works will also focus on using the energy barrier associated with a reaction as an energy criteria (Monte-Carlo criteria).

A wider perspective would consist in adapting this kind of procedure to model other thermosets curing dynamics (poly-vinyl ester, polyurethanes, furan). The main difficulty will deal with the development of training set and ReaxFF force fields dedicated to these molecules.

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